

Informed Health Choices

Contextualizing learning resources

Informed Health Choices primary school resources – Brazilian Portuguese translation process

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Final report, 01. March 2022*

Colophon

Title **Informed Health Choices primary school resources – Brazilian Portuguese translation process**

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Citation Balardin J, Antunes JN (Hospital Albert Einstein). Informed Health Choices primary school resources – Brazilian Portuguese translation process. Final report, Mar 2022. Informed Health Choices Working Paper.

Article category

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- Editorials and commentaries
- Grant applications

Date March 2022

1. Objectives

- To translate the IHC primary school resources into Brazilian Portuguese, in order to make them available for as many children as possible.
- To ensure the quality and understanding of the Brazilian Portuguese IHC primary school resources for children aged 10–12 years.

The Brazilian Portuguese translation process followed the basic steps adopted during the Spanish translation. It included minor adaptations to the context and changing the names of the characters, as well as minor modifications to some of the drawings when required by local regulations. It did not include modifications to the text content.

2. Methods

2.1 Translation process

The core working group of the Brazilian translation process was composed of a translator and a researcher. The first version of the translation has been improved with feedback from different stakeholders: students, schoolteachers, researchers, and health workers (physicians, nurses).

The students only reviewed “The Health Choices Book” and the “Exercise Book”. During an online session, each student reviewed a set of lessons from the textbook and exercises book using a protocol (based on the Norwegian protocol used in schools).

The adult stakeholders that were involved in the Brazilian translation process have provided feedback on the electronic version of the materials in portable electronic format (PDF) using annotation tools. The teachers reviewed the children's book as well as the teachers' guide. Each teacher reviewed a set of lessons. Each healthcare professional and researcher reviewed the complete content of the children and teachers' resources.

2.2. Collecting feedback from networks (students, teachers, researchers, and healthcare workers)

The core working group coded all comments provided by the reviewers and described the results. The code scheme used are described below.

1. Identification of errors in the text (spelling, grammar, translation).
2. Identification of errors in the original text (spelling, grammar or editing).
3. Identification of errors in editing (missing passages, wrong subtitles).
4. Identification of errors in punctuation (coma, quotation).
5. Identification of phrases or concepts that could be improved (for example, modifying the text or including additional text).
6. Make general comments to improve the IHC resources: Although the aim of this review is to gather specific feedback on the language translation, we also invite you to make any other comments of any kind that you have about the resources.
7. Identification of words that could be deleted due to translation problems.
8. Others.

3. Results

The Brazilian translation process started on October 2019 and finished in February 2022. A summary of the results is presented in Table 1. All the feedback comments are available under request and upon approval by the local ethics committee.

The stakeholders also provided additional feedback on several aspects of the translation process and contextualization project. Although we did not use any method to collect and describe these additional comments, we summarized them in items as described below.

Characters' names

Following the discussion raised in the Spanish translation process, we decided to change characters' names to Brazilian Portuguese names.

Formatting of the teacher's guide

Taken into account the criticisms to the teachers' guide Word format raised during the Spanish translation process (e.g. "the material is unfriendly"), we produced an alternative format for this material, mirroring the colour-coded schemes of the children's book.

Add notes to the Brazilian Portuguese translation

To provide additional background information supporting the source text, the following notes were added to the target text:

- Note about the cultural context of the source text: The characters, places, customs and culture of this story are inspired by life in Uganda, Africa.
- Note about the definition of health in lesson 1: In Brazil, the current definitions about health also take into account a social dimension besides its physical and mental aspects.

Minor modifications to the drawings

To comply with local regulations regarding the publication of educational materials for children in Brazil, the following drawings were modified or excluded:

- The Health Choices Book (source text, page 6): labels to describe each object of the first box drawing were included inside the box (e.g. vitamins, injection) in the target text.
- The Health Choices Book (source text, page 12): last box, depicting a character smoking and related text were not included in the target text;
- The Health Choices Book (source text, page 13): labels to describe each object of the drawing were included inside the box in the target text.
- The Health Choices Book (source text, page 15): the figure depicting the Camel ad was excluded in the target text.
- Teachers Guide (page 36 in the target text): the commercial name “Vioxx” was replaced by tablet.

Color formats of the Brazilian translated version of the IHC primary school resources

The materials are in RGB, optimized for screen viewing. We also provide an alternative high resolution CMYK version.

4. Conclusion

This report describes the main actions taken during the Brazilian Portuguese translation process of the IHC primary school resources. It may contribute to further developments of the current version of the materials or to translations of new IHC resources.

Table 1. Results of the Brazilian translation process.

	Initial translation (n, %)	Students review (n, %)	Teachers review (n, %)	Researchers review (n, %)	Health workers review (n, %)
Participants	2	5	3	4	2
Female	2	3	2	2	2
Age	-				
Age of the students professors teach	-	10 - 12	10 - 13		
Start date (First meeting)	October 2019	March 2020	March 2020	February 2020	March 2020
Final date (Last meeting)	February 2020	November 2021	November 2021	November 2021	November 2021
Total comments	781	15	163	378	12
Resource					
The Health Choices Book	100	12	67	186	5
Exercise Book	26	3		27	
Teachers Guide	641		96	105	7
Activity Cards	-				
Poster	4				
Assessment	-				
	781 (100)	15 (100)	163 (100)	378 (100)	12 (100)
Type of comment					
Error in text	281	9	34	30	2
Error in original text			0	11	1
Error formatting	6		0	34	0
Error in punctuation			3	21	2
Text could be improved	441	6	114	254	6
General comment			11	2	0
Text that must be deleted	8		1	22	1
Others	41			4	0
	781 (100)	15 (100)	163 (100)	378 (100)	12 (100)
Suggestions					
Included	781	15	163	374	11
Not included				4	1
Duplicated			51	121	3